

The Role Of Political Propaganda In The Strategy Of The United States Of America Towards Iran After September 11, 2001: A Geopolitical Vision

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 21, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Political ,Strategy, America,geopolitical, Iran</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5590090</p>	<p><i>Political propaganda is one of the most significant tools in psychological warfare since it influences and manages public opinion. Political propaganda of all kinds and its shady forms manifested itself in the speeches of American administrations and electoral campaigns following the events of September 11, 2001, particularly in the speeches of President George W. Bush, the son thirsty for war, and the speeches of others who followed him, through which Afghanistan, Iraq, and Iran were targeted with false information. By the American institutions and government agencies themselves, the main goal of all of this is to maintain geostrategic control over the oil of Iran and other oil countries, and the ability to control global oil prices and available quantities and to ensure that oil reaches the allies of the United States of America, and to prevent it from competitors with the aim of weakening their geostrategic influence.</i></p>

Introduction

In its conflicts with other countries, the United States of America uses various means and methods, including pressure and procrastination, propaganda, persuasion and misinformation; to justify the basis of the American interference in the internal affairs of other countries under various pretexts, such as: terrorism, spreading democracy and bringing about development, or other false allegations. Political propaganda has been used as an effective means of persuasion and misinformation, with the aim of convincing the American and international public opinion of the justice and correctness of its cause; In order to gain his support, mobilize his hatred and direct it against its opponents; to weaken the morale of the targeted countries.

Therefore, political propaganda has not been absent from the electoral and media campaigns of the White House presidential candidates since the outbreak of the War of Independence led by the first president of the United States of America, George Washington, who was described at the time as (the master of deception) until the present time. The most important means used in the electoral campaigns of the candidates of the Republican and Democratic parties of the United States, in addition to being one of the most important means of psychological warfare and soft power adopted to target opponents, political propaganda was used strongly in the speeches and campaigns of President George W. Bush. This was intensified after the United States of America was subjected to terrorist attacks on September 11, 2001, by the terrorist organization Al-Qaeda led by Osama bin Laden, and since then the United States has subjected everything to the war against terrorism, and it reads everything from the requirements of this war, and out of suspicion and suspicion in The other and returning all his movements to evil purposes, and to creating axes of evil, that is, the logic of distrust of the other. President George Bush Jr. launched the term (the global war against terrorism), considering it the most horrific, longest and harshest war that the United States of America entered, and declared the war on terrorism clearly. And he practiced political propaganda as a pretext for the war on Afghanistan in 2001 and the overthrow of the Taliban regime, and then on Iraq in 2003 on the pretext that the latter possessed weapons of mass destruction, and its support for the terrorist al-Qaeda organization, to prove later on the falseness of the allegations that were used against Iraq, and today it uses itself and others, against many countries on top. Iran. The United States of America is trying today, through misleading political propaganda, to confuse and mislead the American and international public opinion in order to persuade it to wage war on Iran over its nuclear program, which it claimed threatens security and stability in the Middle East, and causes harm to the interests of the major countries in the oil-rich Persian Gulf region. Therefore, in its propaganda for the war on Iran, it restores the same previous approach that was used in the war on Iraq during the period from 1991-2003, and uses the principle of simplification to justify its actions and intimidation of Iran's capabilities. In this research, the following questions were answered: What is the role of political propaganda in the strategy of the United States of America towards Iran after September 11, 2001? The answer to that is: The United States has tried and is still trying to deceive the world by using the capabilities of its huge propaganda machine to cover up its real motives and goals from being present in the Arab Gulf region, and to pass its plans to achieve its undeclared strategic goals to dominate the region, by controlling the

oil sources and achieving an advantage. Washington has great economic and political status, and therefore it is trying to occupy Iran to expand its global geostrategic influence, and events have proven beyond any doubt that it has used misleading propaganda to give legal and moral legitimacy to its military interventions, and to place accusations arbitrarily at the countries at odds with it. The research was divided into two demands, dealing with the first requirement: the concept of political propaganda and its emergence, and the second requirement focused on: the role of political propaganda in the United States' strategy towards Iran and its geopolitical dimensions.

2 The first requirement

2.1 The concept of political propaganda and its emergence and development:

Political propaganda is defined as: an attempt to influence public opinion and control the behavior of individuals through the use of purified words and qualified people to perform this type of propaganda to achieve its elected goals. Approval of a loan, voting for a party, volunteering in the army ... etc. (2) It is also defined as: a media attempt to influence people's attitudes, opinions and behavior, and its means is to disseminate information, facts, half-truths, or even lies in an organized attempt to influence public opinion, It is a process of manipulating emotions and feelings in which it is intended to reach to create a state of intellectual tension and emotional charging(3). And Bartlek defines it as: an attempt to influence the opinion and behavior of the group so that individuals take a certain opinion and behavior without the masses thinking about the methods that prompted them to adopt those opinions, beliefs and research in its logic (4). It is also defined as: managing collective attitudes by manipulating important symbols (5). And Walton Douglas defines it as: a communication process aimed at persuading the target audience to adopt the attitudes and beliefs that they chose this is the one who is calling (6).

There is no consensus among researchers on the time of the emergence and emergence of political propaganda, but some believe that political propaganda has been known and used since the earliest ages of history, and it was always and forever in the service of those in authority, but was inherent in the art of government (7), and some believe that the Greeks practiced Political propaganda during the Peloponnesian War that broke out between the Double Alliance led by Athens against the Peloponnesian Union led by Sparta (8). As for the Romans, they used political propaganda to glorify the Roman political system, as well as holding processions and official celebrations; To honor the Roman leaders who achieved victories in wars, and those who came with spoils(9).

Other researchers also believe that political propaganda appeared for the first time with the outbreak of the French Revolution, with which propaganda for revolutionary theories began in France against the existing regimes. B (a new political disease)(10). Germany also realized the importance of the press as an effective means in political propaganda, especially in the field of psychological warfare, as Otto von Bismarck, the Chancellor of the Reich (German Empire) at that time felt the power of the press when the Franco-Prussian war took place in 1870-1871 Germany occupied part of the French territory, and he established a press department at the German Foreign Ministry in the same year, to herald the glory and greatness of Germany throughout the world (11). There are many examples of how fascism and Nazism used symbolic language fully as a weapon in the struggle, and how Mussolini presented a play symbols in Italy, as well as the widespread importance of the swastika in Hitler's rise to power (12). There are those who believe that the actual use of advanced political propaganda began with the outbreak of the First World War (1914-1918), when humanity and propaganda together entered a new phase, and the countries that fought in this war established technical departments for propaganda that worked with scientific methods in both war and peace. After it became clear that modern war depends to a large extent on political propaganda in influencing the masses, on the one hand, and the enemy on the other, and it is not possible to be satisfied with armed military force to win the war or even to maintain the unity and entity of the homeland, and that propaganda is the Fifth Army that guarantees victory in war (13).

The United States of America today is the most prominent country in the use of political propaganda. The American administration and its allies possess a huge and professional propaganda media system in the field of propaganda, which is the largest arsenal in the world. Rather, it has produced articulating tools and tools speaking in various languages for the targeted countries, and managing the war of influence to conquer minds and hearts, to the extent that it is able to influence the policy of the largest power present on the international stage, and mislead American and global public opinion, as they are propaganda tools par excellence that serve to a large extent the directions of American foreign policy , This giant media system contributed to persuading the American public opinion to wage war on Afghanistan and Iraq, and today it uses black propaganda to wage war on Iran (14).

3.The second requirement

3.1 The political propaganda in the US strategy towards Iran

The United States of America has a long history of using political propaganda in war and peace as an important and effective means of psychological warfare to weaken and subjugate hostile countries, and examples of the success of American administrations in using political propaganda to influence public opinion are many, and perhaps former US President Dwight D. The use of political propaganda in the Cold War and succeeded in that, as soon as he took office, he began to focus on the issue of political war by appointing a high-level committee to

study and make recommendations on American information and psychological warfare programs (15). Since 2001, Iran has been subjected to a psychological war launched by the United States of America, as US President George W. Bush launched a political propaganda campaign against Iran, and one of the justifications for this propaganda campaign was his accusation of Iran of supporting al-Qaeda terrorist, in his speech after the United States was exposed to the events of 11 September 2001, he described Iran as one of the three rogue states (Iraq, Iran, North Korea, or the axis of evil countries that sponsor terrorism, as he described it). (16) He emphasized on several occasions that force should be used until Iran reconsiders its policy and described it as the main source of threat in the region. This description and threat to Iran is the turning point in the tense relations based on the mutual threat that emerged after the events of September 11, which is a kind of American lack of acceptance of Iran's role as a major regional power in the region that threatens American interests there. Although the two countries have common strategic and geopolitical interests on the Afghan and Iraqi borders, which Iran considers part of its national security and rejects any presence of US bases there. (17).

In fact, the United States of America has not proven, with official evidence presented to the American and international public opinion, that Iran is dealing with the terrorist al-Qaeda organization, especially since the leaders of Iran condemned the September 11 terrorist attacks on the United States of America, and in an interview with President Khatami after these events, al-Qaeda was called al-Qaeda. Naming the "extremist version of Islam", describing the terrorists who carried out the 9/11 operations as guerrillas who can only deal with their opponents through massacres, and therefore these statements remain within the scope of political propaganda for the president's electoral campaign.

Among the justifications for the US political propaganda against Iran is the US administration's accusation of Iran of regional support for Hezbollah in Lebanon and Iraq, and Hamas's support to undermine peace in the Holy Land, and that the matter calls for increasing pressure on the Islamic Republic of Iran; To change its policy regarding its support for Hezbollah and others, and to prevent it from enriching uranium to produce a nuclear bomb (18).

Iran denies publicly supporting and dealing with Hezbollah in Lebanon and Iraq, especially after the latter was classified as a terrorist organization. Therefore, Iran fears the deterioration of its relations with major countries, but it supports Hezbollah and the armed Shiite factions in Iraq, Lebanon, Bahrain, Yemen and other countries. From an ideological perspective, the truth is that it is looking for its geopolitical interests and objectives in the region as reasons to support the armed factions rather than as intellectual and ideological reasons and motives. Another justification for President Bush's political propaganda regarding the Iranian nuclear program, where he claimed that Iran seeks to produce nuclear weapons by secretly enriching uranium needed for nuclear energy projects, knowing that Iran is one of the signatories to the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty, and Article 4 of the agreement gives every non-nuclear state that signed the agreement the right to develop research, produce and use nuclear energy for peaceful purposes without discrimination between states. (19). The answer is clear that the United States did not prove that Iran produced a nuclear weapon and used it in practice against a country or even threatened it at the very least, and this is what the International Atomic Energy Agency expressed in its report in which it stated that it had no evidence that Iran's nuclear program is used for military purposes, and the report of the US intelligence agency came on March 10, 2009 and confirmed this, in which the Director of National Intelligence Dennis Blair denied Iran's possession of nuclear weapons, although he did not rule out its possession of nuclear weapons in the future. This was before the Armed Forces Committee in the US Senate. (20), and therefore all that was mentioned in President George W. Bush's speech is nothing more than potential and unreal fears for various reasons, including: Iran's secrecy regarding its nuclear program, and its lack of full cooperation with the International Atomic Energy Agency, and this The allegations that the president used to gain the support of the American public are proven false.

Just as the United States and Iran, before the events of September 11, 2001, had started secret talks at a high level based on an Iranian offer to start unconditional negotiations, and a few weeks after the United States invaded Iraq, Iran presented to the United States a new set of proposals for a comprehensive solution to the Middle East problem. On dramatic concessions, Iran made one after another. These concessions included: decisive action against the terrorists in Iran, ending its support for Hamas and Islamic Jihad, a promise to stop its nuclear program, and an explicit agreement to recognize Israel. However, the White House categorically rejected this offer and these Iranian concessions. He submitted an official complaint to the Swiss government against the interference of its ambassador in matters that did not concern him (21).

These Iranian concessions are an indication that Iran was not sticking with its nuclear program after the US invasion of Iraq; because it was in a position of weakness and fear that it would be the next target for the United States after Iraq. This is on the one hand, on the other hand the question that arises: What is the reason for the United States' rejection of the enormous concessions offered by Iran? The answer, I think, is that the strategic goals and interests of the United States in the region are much greater than the concessions of Iran, and even greater than the recognition of Israel; Because it is related to the expansion of its global geostrategic influence, especially in the Arab Gulf region, the most important economic region in the world, which guarantees the survival of its economy on the list of the world's economies, and then grasping the elements of survival in world

leadership, and all this is a clear indication that the Iranian nuclear program was used as political and electoral propaganda. In the speeches of the American administration, Iran, to the present time, when its regional power has grown to some extent, is still calling for unconditional negotiations over its nuclear program, as well as about its geopolitical goals in the region through which it seeks to expand its regional influence, and its desire to be a partner of the United States. In the economic benefit in the region and this is rejected by the United States, which wants to control the sources of oil and its world prices, including Iran's oil, and does not allow anyone to participate in that.

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Another false claim used by President Bush Jr. is what he said in one of his speeches, he said: (The Iranian government is responsible for the death of US forces, by supporting the Iraqi armed factions and providing them with armor-piercing launchers and other weapons), but he did not provide a convincing legal evidence for the community. The international condemns the Iranian government for these actions, so his statements remain mere media and propaganda speeches to win over the American public opinion and gain its support for waging war on Iran and in this speech a kind of political propaganda to stir and manipulate the feelings of the American public opinion in order to gain their support, and this also does not. He denies the targeting of US forces by Iranian-backed groups in light of the increase in tensions between the two countries and the heightened Iranian fears of the possibility of the United States seeking to overthrow the Iranian regime. The media and psychological war to pressure the United States and drag it to the dialogue table to reach an agreement on its nuclear program, and to obtain a guarantee from the first the United States that the latter will not attack it and will not seek to overthrow the existing Iranian regime, lift economic sanctions against it, and establish partnership relations that allow Iran to have regional influence in the region to ensure the interests of both Iran and the United States. However, this major bargain was not accepted by the United States at all. Despite the attempt by President Bush Jr. to give this matter more media and political propaganda than it is, the response came from the American media, which proved the falsehood of the allegations made by the president. Andrew Cockburn wrote in the Los Angeles Times that :) President Bush has clearly decided the bombs known as armor-piercing shells, which have proven to be deadly, especially for American forces in Iraq, are made in Iran and exported to Iraq from Iran, but in November, while American forces were attacking a machine shop in Baghdad, they found a stack of cylinders of this type. The cylinders are easy to manufacture in Iraq and do not need to be imported from Iran. The New York Times also published an article about the same discovery entitled (The United States displays parts of bombs that were said to be made in Iran and admits it is not sure of that) and the newspaper stated that the store contained On materials that removed the ambiguity of the matter, and among the materials were plastic tubes of PVG material, which wrote on the boxes in English that these materials were made in the United Arab Emirates, and other boxes on which it was written "Made in Haditha", an Iraqi city for the Sunni sect. It is located northeast of the Tigris River.

Political propaganda was also present in the arrival of US President Barack Obama to power and the loss of President George W. Bush's elections; this is because President Obama made the best use of the war on Iraq to win the American elections, after he convinced the American public opinion that the Iraq war was unjustified. He said: "The United States of America needs to end the mentality that got us there in the first place." He also said: The Iraq war was motivated by people who prefer military action to diplomacy, and who prefer unilateral American action to hard work of building international consensus). And sought to draw up a new policy for the United States of America in the region based on (rapprochement with Iran), as this rapprochement, as he described it, achieves the strategic goals of the United States, ensures the flow of oil through the Strait of Hormuz, and controls the behavior of some terrorist organizations against US forces stationed in the area. As for President Donald Trump, he used political propaganda against Iran in many places in his speeches and loud media statements, which began with the beginning of his election campaign and even after assuming power to succeed Barack Obama. American Fox TV, saying: (The United States of America should take possession of

any oil produced in Iraq, because it was the leader in the invasion of Iraq, and added: We lost thousands of soldiers, great military people, and tens of thousands of wounded, and I say take the oil because what will happen is that Iran will seize Iraq's oil if we leave, and that the Iranian danger increases at a time when Iran declares itself a nuclear power. Therefore, as soon as Trump assumed power, tension between the two countries renewed, mutual threats returned, and the US foreign policy resorted to political boycotts and sanctions. Economic pressure, pressure and threats to discourage Iran from perpetuating its nuclear program. His last electoral agitation to withdraw after that from the 5 + 1 agreement held by Barack Obama and described it as (discontent), which the United States of America should not have fallen into, and then he imposed devastating economic sanctions on Iran and threatened in front of the media to reduce Iran's oil exports to zero. If it does not stop resuming its nuclear program.

On December 27, an Iranian-backed group in Iraq killed an American contractor, crossing the American red line, an inevitable result in light of heightened tensions between the two countries and the increased risk of miscalculation, although the background to the attack was unclear as to whether the assassination order had been issued. From Tehran or was it carried out independently by Kata'ib Hezbollah, affiliated with the Iraqi Popular Mobilization factions, but the result came with the killing of the Iranian Quds Force commander Qassem Soleimani on January 3, 2020, by direct order of President Trump. This American reaction, described by the US Department of Defense B (Defensive Action), the statement noted Soleimani's responsibility for the deaths of hundreds of Americans and coalition service members and his approval of the US embassy siege in Iraq, and stated that he was actively developing plans to attack American diplomats and service members in Iraq and throughout the region, and the strike, which was carried out during Soleimani leaving Baghdad International Airport, KH party leader Abu Mahdi al-Mohandas, who was also heading the Popular Mobilization Forces, and other Iranian and Iraqi figures. Thus, Iraq formed the stage in which the United States decided This is, after months of escalating tensions, a military confrontation with Iran through the assassination of one of its senior figures charged with implementing Iran's policy in the region. Iran responded by targeting two Iraqi bases hosting American forces with more than ten missiles, and since then, tensions in the Persian Gulf and even in Iraq have remained high. After the arrival of the current President of the United States of America, Joe Biden, the American strategy towards Iran has not changed, as many political analysts expected. President Joe Biden gave his view on the Iranian nuclear program during his election campaign and before winning the recent elections over his rival, Donald Trump. Opinion in September 2020: (If Iran returns to strict compliance with the nuclear agreement, the United States will return to the agreement as a starting point for continuing negotiations with our allies. We will work to strengthen and expand the terms of the nuclear agreement, while addressing other issues of importance) Sanctions will continue to be imposed on Iranian state institutions and high-ranking officials, due to human rights violations, support for terrorism and the development of ballistic missiles (22).

As is the case with his predecessors, Joe Biden, the latter used the Iranian file as a political propaganda in his election campaign to influence American public opinion; this is because his speech included the same reasons that were used by his predecessors, George Bush Jr., Barack Obama, and Donald Trump. However, he chose the terms of his media speech with precision and prior knowledge of the feelings and directions of the American public opinion, which does not want war in light of the Covid-19 pandemic that devastated it, and the Trump administration's failure to deal with it, which is the same behavior that Democrat Barack Obama took to win over George Bush Jr., so Joe Biden was able to convince public opinion that he would deal with the Iranian file rationally if he won the elections, unlike President Trump, who reached a dead end with Iran and the military option became the only solution. To deter Iran and this is what was rejected by the American public opinion, which was rejecting the war in many opinion polls.

4. Conclusions:

1 - The United States has a huge and professional propaganda media system in the field of propaganda, which is the largest arsenal in the world. It has always been harnessed to pass the plans of the wars of the United States of America and to target its victims by shading American and international public opinion. It largely serves the directions of American foreign policy as a means of Soft power means, which have contributed to persuading the American public opinion to wage war on Afghanistan and Iraq, and today black propaganda is being used to wage war on Iran.

2- Iran has been subjected since 2001 to a psychological war launched against it by the United States of America, which intensified after 2004, as President George W. Bush launched a political propaganda campaign against Iran and accused it of various accusations, but it did not prove with legal evidence the validity of these allegations, and therefore these allegations remain. It is part of the psychological war plans against Iran, and its goal is to influence American and international public opinion, in order to gain legitimacy for the movement of its military forces, and to achieve its geostrategic goals in the region.

3- The Iranian nuclear program was used as political and electoral propaganda in the speeches of all American administrations after the events of September 11, 2001, at the same time Iran is still using the policy of tug-of-

war with the United States, and calls for unconditional negotiation, to preserve Iranian gains, especially economic ones in the region, and to achieve its goals The geopolitics through which it seeks to expand its regional influence, as well as Iran's desire to be a partner of the United States of America in the economic benefit in the region, and this is rejected by the United States, which wants to control the sources of oil and its global prices, including Iran's oil, and does not allow anyone to participate in it that.

4- The United States and Iran, before the events of September 11, 2001, had started secret talks at a high level based on an Iranian offer to start unconditional negotiations, in which Iran made huge dramatic concessions, one after the other, which included: Iran taking decisive action against the terrorists, and ending its support for Hamas and Jihad The Islamic State promised to stop its nuclear program and an explicit agreement to recognize Israel. However, the White House categorically rejected this offer and these Iranian concessions.

5- Iran was not sticking to its nuclear program after the United States invaded Iraq; Because it was in a position of weakness and fear that it will be the next target of the United States after Iraq, and that the strategic goals and interests of the United States in the region are much greater than Iran's concessions, and even greater than Iran's recognition of Israel; Because it is related to the expansion of its global geostrategic influence, and in particular in the Arab Gulf region, the most important economic region in the world, which guarantees it the survival of global hegemony.

6- Iran is trying through its continued enrichment of uranium and escalation of its attacks against the United States by relying on its proxies in Iraq to obtain guarantees from the United States of America that the latter will not attack it and will not seek to overthrow the existing Iranian regime, lift economic sanctions and establish partnership relations between the two countries that allow Iran to have Regional influence in the region to ensure that the interests of Iran and the United States are secured together. However, this great bargaining was not accepted by the United States at all.

7- The American threats of a preemptive strike on Iran are nothing more than propaganda lies and are part of the requirements of psychological warfare and soft power that the United States uses to intensify pressure on Iran and subject it to remain within the equilibrium relations determined by the United States of America.

8- The continuation of the US-Iranian tension and conflict will cause huge financial costs to the United States of America, and may cause the United States of America to be unable to spend on its forces stationed in the region, weaken its influence and influence, and then become preoccupied with Iran, and this is what Iran is working on, while China is unique Russia is the real competitors of the United States in expanding their geostrategic influence in different regions of the world.

To the present time, tensions between the United States and Iran are still at their highest levels. Each party adheres to its opinion and there are no solutions in sight as long as the Jubaiden administration adheres to Iran's compliance with the (5+1) agreement without conditions and as determined by the United States, and stops its destabilizing activities in the Middle East region. While Iran refrains from providing some of the information requested by the International Energy Organization about its nuclear program; because she believes that her answer to these questions is a blatant and illegal interference in her internal affairs.

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